

TYPES OF PHRASEOLOGISMS FROM THE STRUCTURAL SIDE (IN THE BASIS OF THE WORKS OF I. YUSUPOV)

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Abstract: Along with the lexical-semantic side of phraseological word combinations, determining their grammatical structure is one of the most important issues. When we look at the phraseological materials of the Karakalpak language, it can be seen that there are many types of them both in terms of meaning and structure. Searching phraseological word combinations only in the semantic aspect is insufficient in revealing their nature and in-depth study. That's why they need to be evaluated in terms of their form. In this case, I have analyzed the examples taken from the works of I. Yusupov.

In the practice of scientific research, it is more noticeable to distinguish phraseological units according to their structure into the two most relevant grammatical types: phraseological units in the form of word combinations, phraseological units in the form of sentences [1.2.3]. Without learning the structure and forms of phraseologisms, it is difficult to determine their nature, peculiarities and characteristics [4; 184]. Therefore, along with the lexical-semantic method of phraseological word combinations, determining their grammatical structure is one of the most important issues. In fact, scientific researchers have observed that phraseological word combinations in the Karakalpak language are found in various types according to their morphological features.

When we look at the phraseological materials of the Karakalpak language, it can be seen that there are many types of them both in terms of meaning and structure. Searching phraseological word combinations only in the semantic aspect is insufficient in revealing their nature and in-depth study. That's why they need to be evaluated in terms of their form.

It is convenient to divide phraseological word combinations in the modern Karakalpak language into three types from the point of structure:

1. Phraseological phrases in the form of word combination: tas bawır (strict), qulaq túriw (listen), kóz astınan qaraw (look under the eyes), astarlı sóz (metaphor), qula duz (flatness), sırdanday dala (wide field), bawırı qan bolıw (suffer), til ushı (top of the tongue), qamırdan qıl suwırǵanday (excellent), iyni keliw (fit), etc.

2. Phraseologisms in the form of a simple sentence: bar bilgeni awzında (talkative), búyiri burdı (be kind), adım atlandı (proceeded), at aylanıp qazıǵın tabadı (one can return back), zer qádirin zerger biler (jeweler knows the value of gold), etc.

3. Phraseologism in the form of a compound sentence: zarım barda, zorım joq (I have an offer, but not force), kósherimdi jel bilsin, etegi elpi, jeńi jelpi (let the wind know my move).

Samaldan sorayman shóllerge barıp, I ask from wind going to deserts,

Juldızlarǵa qarap oyǵa talaman.

Looking at the stars, I think. «Dáwir samalları».

(Winds of the Age).

In the example, the two-component phraseology "oyǵa talaman" is used as a predicative in the sentence.

Phraseologisms in the form of word combination consist of a stable order of two or more words. They often serve as a certain part of speech. For example: ún joq, tún joq; (no sound, no night); tamaǵı toq, kóylegi kók, (he's full, his shirt is blue), etc. In the form of a simple sentence, depending on the change of the form and use of the component from the verb in the composition of some phraseological word combination, it can be a separate word combination and become similar to some sentence. For example: awzı jalasıw-awız jalastı; bas kóteriw-bas kóterdi; dizesi qaltıraw-dizesi qaltıradı, etc.

Therefore, the change and use of verb components plays a big role in the fact that phraseological word combinations are equal to individual word combination or some sentence.

We can see that from the morphological point of view, the phraseological units that are found in the form of word combination from the structural side in the Karakalpak language are met in various forms from the various parts of speech. In addition, they vary in terms of the number of components (words) in their composition. Taking into account the number of components, we decided to divide them into three types: 1. Two-component phraseologisms: til ushı (fake), peyli tar (jealous), bawırına basıw (embrace), ekiniń biri (once), qulaq salıw (obey), júregi sháwkildew (be happy), gúderin úziw (hopeless), arqa súyew (rely on) and so on. 2. Three-component phraseology: sirkesi suw kótermew (ignore), murnına samal eniw (grow up), qızıl gegirdek bolıw (to brag), kózin ashıp jumǵansha (in a short time), istiń kózin biliw (intelligent), qudaydıń qutlı kúni (every day), tóbesi kókke jetiw (excited), bir pul bolıw (disappointed), janı kózine kóriniw (frightened), qan sorpa bolıw (sweating), júregi alıp ushıw (very happy), qamırdan qıl suwırǵanday (smooth), tayaǵın iyt qayzaw (unlucky) and so on. 3. Multi-component phraseologisms: Jan iynine ot túsiw (worry), til menen oraq orıw (perform orally), bir tırnaqqa zar bolıw (want to have baby), eki kózi tórt bolıw (wait), eki ayaǵın bir etikke tıǵıw (to scare), on gúlinen bir gúli ashılmaǵan (young), kemege mingenniń janı bir (similar destination), iytten bir súyek qarızdar bolıw (have debt), etc.

When we pay attention to the structural differences of multi-component phraseological units, we see that they are related to one verb form of several words, like verb groups in our language. In verb groups, each word preserves its individual lexical meaning and is semantically related to the verb, answers a question, and is used in the service of part of speech in the sentence. For example: Xalıqtıń xızmetinde bolıw, Watan ushın xızmet etiw, adamlar menen jaqsı qatnasta bolmaytuǵın, jas waqtınan miynetke shınıqqan (To be in the service of the people, to serve the country, not to be treated better by people, trained from early ages), etc. Among the phraseological word combinations, we also meet multi-component phraseological units in the structure like this.

The verb components in phraseological word combinations are usually given in the form of the infinitive verb -ıw, -iw, -w, but depending on their connection with other words in the sentence, they can change with any verb form. Phraseological word combinations under the control of infinitive verb -ıw, -iw, -w: kózden ǵayıp bolıw, kindik qanı tamıw, kózi tas tóbesine shıǵıw, tıp degende tıpirik jerge túspew, ayaqqa jip taǵıp oynaw, betiniń sarısın bes eli tógiw, tórt túligi say bolıw, (disappear, be born, scared, very cold, to wander, make to be ashamed, be fit) etc.

The phraseological word combinations in this structure are also used in poetic works. For example:

Aldında bas iyiw-maqtanish mağan,	Bow in front of him – is praise to me,
Jumis muzañ shiray qossin shirayğa.	Let your work adds beauty to your beauty.
Bir zamanda Uzaq degen bay bolıp,	Once upon a time, there was rich Uzak,
Ótken edi tórt túligi say bolıp.	Passed as formed. «Joldas muğallim» (Comrade Teacher)

In the examples, the phraseology "bowing in front of him" is used as subject in the sentence, and the phraseology "be formed" is used as modifier.

Phraseological word combinations under the control of participle form verbs consist of three and more components. Phraseological word combinations under the control of -ğan, -gen participle forms of the verb: eki kemeniñ basın uslağan, awzınan sarısı ketpegen, awzınan nanı túsken, on gúlinen bir gúli ashılmağan. (do two action simultaneously, young, dull, young).

For example: Men qız emespen góy, hayalman aqırı, I'm not a girl, I'm woman at all,
On gúlden bir gúli ashılmağan jas. I'm very young.

Sen qalaysha mağan bolasañ joldas? How can you be my friend? «Aktrisanıñ ıǵbalı» (Actress' luck).

In the examples, "on gúlinen bir gúli ashılmağan" is used in the service of attribute. Also, phraseological word combinations under the control of the participle form of verb in the form of -tuǵın: qoy awzınan shóp almaytuǵın, pıshıq murnı batpaytuǵın (very kind and shy, thick), etc., phraseological word combinations under the control of the verb in the form of - gánday, -gendey: júzikke qas qondırǵanday, iyne menen qudıq qazǵanday, túyeden postın taslaǵanday, qamırdan qıl suwırǵanday, qulaqqa urǵan tanaday, jerden jeti qoyan tapqanday (match, do the very difficult task, ignore, excellent, quiet, happy), etc.

Baylağan shomlarda óship janar may, went out burning oil in the dark evenings,
Ses tınar qulaqqa urǵan tanaday. The sound stopped, was very quiet.

Qoldan baylaǵandı tis penen sheshkendey, Like untying a handcuff with teeth,

Misli digirmannan tiri túskendey. It's like staying alive after difficulties. «Aktrisanıñ ıǵbalı»

In poet's works, phraseological word combinations in the form of simple sentences are also skillfully used by matching them to poem lines.

If the phraseological word combinations that are found in the form of a simple sentence come in the form of a direct simple sentence, then depending on the change of the form and use of the component from the verbs in the second ones, it becomes a separate word combination and becomes some sentence [5; 147]. For example:

Ayaǵı jerge tiymew – ayaǵı jerge tiymedi (be busy)

Júregi jarılıw – júregi jarıldı (be happy)

Kóz qıyıǵın salıw – kóz qıyıǵın saldı (glance).

The variable use of verb components plays an important role in making the phraseological word combinations equal to the single word combination or some sentence.

Kemeler qawsaǵan qayırdá tozıp, The ships are worn out in missing place,

Kórseñ júrek sizlar dártleriñ qozıp. If you see it, hurts your heart. «Aral elegiyaları»

It can be seen that some proverbs, which have lexical-grammatical stability, and some words with a deep meaning, which have been made by some people and become proverbs, are found in the form of separate sentence. For example:

Bar bilgeni awzında, tells everything even secret,

Sawdıraq qaraqalpağım. My open-hearted Karakalpak. "Begligiñdi buzba sen"

Meyli soqpasa ne paydası bar, What's the use if it doesn't make,

Báribir aylanıp qazıgın tabar. Anyway, he return back. «Aktrisanıñ ıǵbalı»

Bar bilgeni awzında, at aylanıp qazıgın tabar – are phraseology in the form of a simple sentence. They are phraseologisms in the form of simple sentence with one part of speech.

Alaqanda saqlaymız sizdi, We will keep you in the palm of our hands

Hám áudik emendi bir aylandıń da, And you turned the audic oak,

Kózden ğayıp boldıń. Uzaq izledim. You disappeared from sight. I searched for a long time.

«Anna Axmatovanı oqıǵanda»

Although phraseological units in the form of a compound sentence are met in the form of compound sentence in terms of grammatical structure makes a vocabulary, grammatical fullness. Phraseological word combination in the form of a compound sentence often includes phraseological word combination with two equal components. For example: qazan da may, shómish te may, sen je, men je, ay deytuǵın áje joq, qoy deytuǵın xoja joq (there is oil in the pot, oil in the pan, you eat, I eat, there is no one who says no), etc.

Phraseologisms in this type of composition are rarely used in poetry works.

For example: Kel, sen sáwbetles bol bizge, háy samal, Come, talk with us, hey wind,

Eglerge zorım joq, zarım bar meniń. I don't have force for one, I have a need.

«Ájiniyaz shayırdıń samalǵa shaǵınıw»

For example, the phraseology "we have a need and we don't have force" is used in a different order. Also, in the works of poet, one component of two-component phraseological units is removed and other words related to the context are used.

For example: Kúshliler ázzini qaqqaplap shetke, The braves knock down the poor aside,

«Qoy derge xoja joq» degen usı dá, "There is no one to say no " is this,

«Kórsetken ráhátli kúniń usı ma?» "Is this the happy day you showed?"

We can also see the types that the words in the components of equal two-component phraseological units are given by exchanging with other words in poet works. For example:

Kósherimiz jelge málim edik biz, Everyone knows our move,

Qonarımız sayǵa málim dedik biz. We say that everyone knows our stay.

«Noǵaylarǵa»

In this example, the phraseology «kósherimizdi jel bilsin, qonarımdı say bilsin» is used in a modified way. A different group of phraseological word combination is made up of poem lines in which proverbs and sayings are used in poet works.

For example: Qolawın tapsañ qar janar, If you find a way, the snow will burn.

Júyesiz ursañ balta snar. If you hit without a system, the ax will break.

Sóyley-sóyley sheshen bolar, Becomes orator after talking much,

Kósem bolar kóre-kóre. Becomes wise after seeing much.

Kewil-kewilden suw isher, Heart enjoys from heart,

Serle háy insan balası, Watch out, hey human being

Jamandur kewil alasi. Upset heart is bad.

In his works, I. Yusupov, along with the use of such common folk phraseological units, used different word combinations and full sentences, combining them from the semantic point of view, turning them into a unit that interprets a connected meaning. Such deep and artistic meaningful word combinations, created by the poet, serve as an artistic tool in the language.

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